

e^* -CONNECTEDNESS IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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ABSTRACT. In this paper the concept of types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -extremally disconnected in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces are introduced and studied. Here we introduce the concepts of intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_S -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_M -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -strongly connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -super connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_i -connectedness ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$), and obtain several properties and some characterizations concerning connectedness in these spaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since the introduction of fuzzy sets by Zadeh [15], the fuzzy concept has invaded almost all branches of mathematics. The concept of fuzzy topological spaces was introduced and developed by Chang [2]. Atanassov [1] introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Coker [3] introduced the intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. Several types of fuzzy connectedness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces were defined by Turnali and Coker [14]. The initiation of e^* -open sets in topological spaces is due to Ekici [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Sobana et.al [12] were introduced the concept of fuzzy e^* -open sets in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces (briefly, IFTS's). In this paper we have introduced some types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -extremally disconnected spaces and studied their properties and characterizations.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We recall the following definition.

Definition 2.1. [1] Let X be a nonempty fixed set and I be the closed interval in $[0, 1]$. An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) A is an object of the following form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle ; x \in X \}$ where the mappings $\mu_A(x) : X \rightarrow I$ and $\nu_A(x) : X \rightarrow I$ denote the degree of membership (namely) $\mu_A(x)$ and the degree of non membership (namely) $\nu_A(x)$ for each element $x \in X$ to the set A respectively, and $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$.

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Definition 2.2. [1] Let A and B are intuitionistic fuzzy sets of the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Then

- (i) $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x)$;
- (ii) \overline{A} (or A^c) = $\{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$;
- (iii) $A \cap B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$;
- (iv) $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$;
- (v) $[]A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), 1 - \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$;
- (vi) $\langle \rangle A = \{ \langle x, 1 - \nu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$;

We will use the notation $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle : x \in X \}$ instead of $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.

Definition 2.3. [4] $\mathbb{0} = \{ \langle x, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $\mathbb{1} = \{ \langle x, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$. Let $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ such that $\alpha + \beta \leq 1$. An intuitionistic fuzzy point $(IFP)_{p(\alpha, \beta)}$ is

intuitionistic fuzzy set defined by $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}(x) = \begin{cases} (\alpha, \beta) & \text{if } x=p \\ (0, 1) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Definition 2.4. [3] An intuitionistic fuzzy topology (IFT) in Coker's sense on a nonempty set X is a family T of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $\mathbb{0}, \mathbb{1} \in T$;
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in T$, for any $G_1, G_2 \in T$;
- (iii) $\cup G_i \in T$ for any arbitrary family $\{G_i; i \in J\} \subseteq T$.

In this paper by (X, T) or simply by X we will denote the intuitionistic fuzzy topological space (IFTS). Each IFS which belongs to T is called an intuitionistic fuzzy open set (IFOS) in X . The complement \overline{A} of an IFOS A in X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy closed set (IFCS) in X .

Definition 2.5. [10] Let $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ be an IFP in IFTS X . An IFS A in X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy neighborhood (IFN) of $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ if there exists an IFOS B in X such that $p_{(\alpha, \beta)} \in B \subseteq A$.

Let X and Y are two non-empty sets and $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be a function [3]. If $B = \{ \langle y, \mu_B(y), \nu_B(y) \rangle : y \in Y \}$ is an IFS in Y , then the pre-image of B under f is denoted and defined by $f^{-1}(B) = \{ \langle x, f^{-1}(\mu_B(x)), f^{-1}(\nu_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Since $\mu_B(x), \nu_B(x)$ are fuzzy sets, we explain that $f^{-1}(\mu_B(x)) = \mu_B(x)(f(x)), f^{-1}(\nu_B(x)) = \nu_B(x)(f(x))$.

Definition 2.6. [3] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an IFS in X . Then the intuitionistic fuzzy closure and intuitionistic fuzzy interior of A are defined by

- (i) $cl(A) = \bigcap \{ C : C \text{ is an IFCS in } X \text{ and } C \supseteq A \}$;
- (ii) $int(A) = \bigcup \{ D : D \text{ is an IFOS in } X \text{ and } D \subseteq A \}$;

It can be also shown that $cl(A)$ is an IFCS, $int(A)$ is an IFOS in X and A is an IFCS in X if and only if $cl(A) = A$; A is an IFOS in X if and only if $int(A) = A$

Proposition 2.1. [3] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and A, B be intuitionistic fuzzy sets in X . Then the following properties hold:

- (i) $cl(\overline{A}) = \overline{(int(A))}$, $int(\overline{A}) = \overline{(cl(A))}$;
- (ii) $int(A) \subseteq A \subseteq cl(A)$.

Definition 2.7. [12] Let A be an IFS in an IFTS (X, T) . A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open set (IFe*OS, for short) in X if $A \subseteq cl_{intcl_\delta}(A)$. The Complement of A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -closed set (IFe*CS, for short) in X .

Definition 2.8. Let A be IFS in an IFTS (X, T) . A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy regular open set [13] (briefly IFROS) if $A = intcl(A)$ and intuitionistic fuzzy regular closed set (briefly IFRCS) if $A = cl_{int}(A)$

Definition 2.9. [13] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ be a IFS in X . Then the fuzzy δ closure of A are denoted and defined by $cl_\delta(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is an IFRCS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$ and $int_\delta(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is an IFROS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$.

Definition 2.10. [3] Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be IFTS's. A function $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is called intuitionistic fuzzy continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is an IFOS in X for every $B \in S$.

Lemma 2.2. [14]

- (i) $A \cap B = \emptyset \Rightarrow A \subseteq \overline{B}$.
- (ii) $A \not\subseteq B \Rightarrow A \cap B \neq \emptyset$

Definition 2.11. [4] Two intuitionistic fuzzy sets A and B are said to be q-coincident (AqB) if and only if there exists an element $x \in X$ such that $\mu_A(x) > \nu_B(x)$ or $\nu_A(x) < \mu_B(x)$. If A and B are said to be not q-coincident ($A\bar{q}B$) if and only if $A \subseteq B$.

Definition 2.12. [11] An IFTS (X, T) is called intuitionistic fuzzy C_5 -connected between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets A and B if there is no IFOS E in (X, T) such that $A \subseteq E$ and $E\bar{q}B$.

3. TYPES OF INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY e^* -CONNECTEDNESS IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 3.1. Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be IFTS's. A function $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is called intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is an IFe*OS in X for every $B \in S$.

Definition 3.2. Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle$ be an IFS in X . Then the intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -interior and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -closure are defined and denoted by:

$$e^*cl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is an IFe*CS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$$

and

$$e^*int(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is an IFe*OS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}.$$

It is clear that A is an IFe*CS (IFe*OS) in X iff $A = cl_{e^*}(A)$ ($A = int_{e^*}(A)$).

Definition 3.3. Let A be IFS in an IFTS (X, T) . A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular open set (briefly IFe*ROS) if $A = e^*int(e^*cl(A))$ and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular closed set (briefly IFe*RCS) if $A = e^*cl(e^*int(A))$

Definition 3.4. An IFTS (X, T) is IFe*-disconnected if there exists intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets P, Q in X , $P \neq \emptyset, Q \neq \emptyset$ such that $P \cup Q = \mathbf{1}$ and $P \cap Q = \emptyset$. If X is not IFe*-disconnected then it is said to be IFe*-connected.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $T = \{\emptyset, \mathbf{1}, P\}$ where $P = \{\langle x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.4}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X\}$, $Q = \{\langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X\}$, P and Q are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X , $P \neq \emptyset, Q \neq \emptyset$ and $P \cup Q = P \neq \mathbf{1}, P \cap Q = Q \neq \emptyset$. Hence X is IFe*-connected.

Example 3.6. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}), (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}), (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, Q and R are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X , $Q \neq \emptyset$, $R \neq \emptyset$ and $Q \cup R = \mathbf{1}$, $Q \cap R = \emptyset$. Hence X is IFe^* -disconnected.

Definition 3.7. An IFTS (X, T) is IFe^*C_5 -disconnected if there exists IFS P in X , which is both IFe^* OS and IFe^* CS such that $P \neq \emptyset$, and $P \neq \mathbf{1}$. If X is not IFe^*C_5 -disconnected then it is said to be IFe^*C_5 -connected.

Example 3.8. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, x \in X \}$ Q is an IFe^* OS in X , but Q is not IFe^* CS since $\text{clint}(cl_\delta(Q)) \not\subseteq Q$

Example 3.9. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}), (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, Q is an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X . Also Q is IFe^* CS since $\text{clint}(cl_\delta(Q)) = \emptyset \leq Q$. Hence there exists an IFS Q in X such that $\mathbf{1} \neq Q \neq \emptyset$ which is both IFe^* OS and IFe^* CS in X . Thus X is IFe^*C_5 -disconnected.

Proposition 3.1. IFe^*C_5 -connectedness implies IFe^* -connectedness.

Proof. Suppose that there exists nonempty intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets P and Q such that $P \cup Q = \mathbf{1}$ and $P \cap Q = \emptyset$ (IFe^* -disconnected) then $\mu_P \vee \mu_Q = \mathbf{1}$, $\nu_P \wedge \nu_Q = \emptyset$ and $\mu_P \vee \mu_Q = \emptyset$, $\nu_P \wedge \nu_Q = \mathbf{1}$. In other words $\bar{Q} = P$. Hence P is IFe^* -clopen which implies X is IFe^*C_5 -disconnected. \square

But the converse need not be true as shown by the following example.

Example 3.10. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, P and Q are IFe^* OS in X . Also $P \cup Q \neq \mathbf{1} = P$, $P \cap Q \neq \emptyset = Q$. Hence X is IFe^* -connected. Since IFS P is both IFe^* OS and IFe^* CS in X , X is IFe^*C_5 -disconnected.

Proposition 3.2. Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be a IFe^* -irresolute surjection, (X, T) is an IFe^* -connected, then (Y, S) is IFe^* -connected.

Proof. Assume that (Y, S) is not IFe^* -connected then there exists nonempty intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets P and Q in (Y, S) such that $P \cup Q = \mathbf{1}$ and $P \cap Q = \emptyset$. Since f is IFe^* -irresolute mapping, $R = f^{-1}(P) \neq \emptyset$, $U = f^{-1}(Q) \neq \emptyset$ which are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X . And $f^{-1}(P) \cup f^{-1}(Q) = f^{-1}(\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$ which implies $R \cup U = \mathbf{1}$. $f^{-1}(P) \cap f^{-1}(Q) = f^{-1}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$ which implies $R \cap U = \emptyset$. Thus X is IFe^* -disconnected, which is a contradiction to our hypothesis. Hence Y is IFe^* -connected. \square

Proposition 3.3. (X, T) is IFe^*C_5 -connected iff there exists no nonempty intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets P and Q in X such that $P = \bar{Q}$

Proof. Suppose that P and Q are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X such that $P \neq \emptyset \neq Q$ and $P = \bar{Q}$. Since $P = \bar{Q}$, \bar{Q} is an IFe^* OS and Q is an IFe^* CS, and $P \neq \emptyset$ implies $Q \neq \mathbf{1}$. But this is a contradiction to the fact that X is IFe^*C_5 -connected. Conversely, let P be both IFe^* OS and IFe^* CS in X such that $\emptyset \neq P \neq \mathbf{1}$. Now take $Q = \bar{P}$. Q is an IFe^* OS and $P \neq \mathbf{1}$ which implies $Q = \bar{P} \neq \emptyset$ which is a contradiction. \square

Definition 3.11. An IFTS (X, T) is IFe^* -strongly connected if there exists no nonempty IFe^* CS's P and Q in X such that $\mu_P + \mu_Q \leq 1$, $\nu_P + \nu_Q \geq 1$

In otherwords, an IFTS (X, T) is IFe^* -strongly connected if there exists no nonempty IFe^* CS's P and Q in X such that $P \cap Q = \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.4. *An IFTS (X, T) is IFe^* -strongly connected if there exists no IFe^* OS's P and Q in X , $P \neq \perp \neq Q$ such that $\mu_P + \mu_Q \geq 1$, $\nu_P + \nu_Q \leq 1$*

Example 3.12. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, P is an IFe^* OS in X . P and Q is an IFe^* OS in X since $Q \subseteq clint(cl_\delta(Q))$. Also $\mu_P + \mu_Q \leq 1$, $\nu_P + \nu_Q \geq 1$. Hence X is IFe^* -strongly connected.

Proposition 3.5. *Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be a IFe^* -irresolute surjection. If X is an IFe^* -strongly connected, then so is Y .*

Proof. Suppose that Y is not IFe^* -strongly connected then there exists IFe^* CS C and D in Y such that $C \neq \emptyset$, $D \neq \emptyset$, $C \cap D = \emptyset$. Since f is IFe^* -irresolute, $f^{-1}(C)$, $f^{-1}(D)$ are IFe^* CSs in X and $f^{-1}(C) \cap f^{-1}(D) = \emptyset$, $f^{-1}(C) \neq \emptyset$, $f^{-1}(D) \neq \emptyset$. (If $f^{-1}(C) = \emptyset$, then $f(f^{-1}(C)) = C$ which implies $f(\emptyset) = C$. So $C = \emptyset$ a contradiction) Hence X is IFe^* -strongly disconnected, a contradiction. Thus (Y, S) is IFe^* -strongly connected. \square

IFe^* -strongly connected does not imply IFe^*C_5 -connected, and IFe^*C_5 -connected does not imply IFe^* -strongly connected. For this purpose we see the following examples:

Example 3.13. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, X is IFe^*C_5 -connected. Since $Q \subseteq clint(cl_\delta(Q))$. Also $\mu_P + \mu_Q \leq 1$, $\nu_P + \nu_Q \geq 1$. Hence X is IFe^* -strongly connected. But X is not IFe^*C_5 -connected, since Q is both IFe^* OS and IFe^* CS in X .

Example 3.14. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, X is IFe^*C_5 -connected. But X is not IFe^* -strongly connected since Q and R are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X such that $\mu_Q + \mu_R \geq 1$, $\nu_Q + \nu_R \leq 1$.

Definition 3.15. P and Q are non-zero intuitionistic fuzzy sets in (X, T) . Then P and Q are said to be

- (i) IFe^* -weakly separated if $e^*cl(P) \subseteq \overline{Q}$ and $e^*cl(Q) \subseteq \overline{P}$.
- (ii) IFe^* -q-separated if $(e^*cl(P)) \cap Q = \emptyset = P \cap (e^*cl(Q))$.

Definition 3.16. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be IFe^*C_5 -disconnected if there exists IFe^* -weakly separated non-zero intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q in (X, T) such that $P \cup Q = \perp$.

Example 3.17. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, Q and R are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X , $e^*cl(Q) \subseteq R$ and $e^*cl(R) \subseteq Q$. Hence Q and R are IFe^* -weakly separated and $Q \cup R = \perp$. So X is IFe^*C_5 -disconnected.

Definition 3.18. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be IFe^*C_M -disconnected if there exists IFe^* -q-separated non-zero intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q in (X, T) such that $P \cup Q = \perp$.

Example 3.19. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, Q and R are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X , $(e^*cl(Q)) \cap R = \emptyset$ and $Q \cap (e^*cl(R)) = \emptyset$ which implies Q and R are IFe^* -q-separated and $Q \cup R = \perp$. Hence X is IFe^*C_M -disconnected.

Remark. *An IFTS (X, T) is IFe^*C_S -connected if and only if (X, T) is IFe^*C_M -connected.*

Definition 3.20. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be IFe^* -super disconnected if there exists an IFe^* -regular open set P in X such that $\mathbb{0} \neq P \neq \mathbb{1}$. X is called IFe^* -super connected if X is not IFe^* -super disconnected.

Example 3.21. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, Q and R are intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in X and $e^*int(e^*cl(Q)) = Q$. This implies Q is an IFe^* -regular open set in X . Hence X is an IFe^* -super disconnected.

Proposition 3.6. Let (X, T) be an IFTS. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) X is IFe^* -super connected
- (ii) For each IFe^* OS $P \neq \mathbb{0}$ in X , we have $e^*clP = \mathbb{1}$
- (iii) For each IFe^* CS $P \neq \mathbb{1}$ in X , we have $e^*intP = \mathbb{0}$
- (iv) There exists no IFe^* OS's P and Q in X such that $P \neq \mathbb{0} \neq Q$ and $P \subseteq \overline{Q}$
- (v) There exists no IFe^* OS's P and Q in X such that $P \neq \mathbb{0} \neq Q, Q = \overline{e^*clP}$ and $P = \overline{e^*clQ}$
- (vi) There exists no IFe^* CS's P and Q in X such that $P \neq \mathbb{1} \neq Q, Q = \overline{e^*intP}$ and $P = \overline{e^*intQ}$

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Assume that there exists an $P \neq \mathbb{0}$ such that $e^*cl(P) \neq \mathbb{1}$. Take $P = e^*int(e^*cl(P))$. Then P is proper e^* -regular open set in X which contradicts that X is IFe^* -super connectedness.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let $P \neq \mathbb{1}$ be an IFe^* CS in X . If we take $Q = \overline{P}$ then Q is an IFe^* OS in X and $Q \neq \mathbb{0}$. Hence by (ii) $e^*cl(Q) = \mathbb{1} \Rightarrow \overline{e^*cl(Q)} = \mathbb{0} \Rightarrow e^*int(\overline{Q}) = \mathbb{0} \Rightarrow e^*int(A) = \mathbb{0}$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv): Let P and Q are IFe^* OS in X such that $P \neq \mathbb{0} \neq Q$ and $P \subseteq \overline{Q}$. Since \overline{Q} is an IFe^* CS in X , $\overline{Q} \neq \mathbb{1}$ by (iii) $e^*int\overline{Q} = \mathbb{0}$. But $P \subseteq \overline{Q}$ implies $\mathbb{0} \neq P = e^*int(P) \subseteq e^*int(\overline{Q}) = \mathbb{0}$ which is a contradiction.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i): Let $\mathbb{0} \neq P \neq \mathbb{1}$ be an IFe^* -regular open set in X . If we take $Q = \overline{e^*cl(P)}$, we get $Q \neq \mathbb{0}$. (If not $Q = \mathbb{0}$ implies $e^*cl(P) = \mathbb{0} \Rightarrow e^*cl(P) = \mathbb{1} \Rightarrow P = e^*int(e^*cl(P)) = e^*int(\mathbb{1}) = \mathbb{1} \Rightarrow P = \mathbb{1}$ a contradiction to $P \neq \mathbb{1}$). We also have $P \subseteq \overline{Q}$ which is also a contradiction. Therefore X is IFe^* -super connected.

(i) \Rightarrow (v): Let P and Q be two IFe^* OS in (X, T) such that $P \neq \mathbb{0} \neq Q, Q = \overline{e^*cl(P)}$ and $P = \overline{e^*cl(Q)}$. Now we have $e^*int(e^*cl(P)) = e^*int(\overline{Q}) = \overline{e^*cl(Q)} = P, P \neq \mathbb{0}$ and $P \neq \mathbb{1}$, since if $P = \mathbb{1}$ then $\mathbb{1} = \overline{e^*cl(Q)} \Rightarrow e^*cl(Q) = \mathbb{0} \Rightarrow Q = \mathbb{0}$. But $Q \neq \mathbb{0}$. Therefore $P \neq \mathbb{1} \Rightarrow P$ is proper IFe^* -regular open set in (X, T) which is contradiction to (i). Hence (v) is true.

(v) \Rightarrow (i): Let P be IFe^* OS in X such that $P = e^*int(e^*cl(P)), \mathbb{0} \neq P \neq \mathbb{1}$. Now take $Q = \overline{e^*cl(P)}$. In this case, we get $Q \neq \mathbb{0}$ and Q is an IFe^* OS in X and $Q = \overline{e^*cl(P)}$ and $e^*cl(Q) = e^*cl(\overline{e^*cl(P)}) = \overline{(e^*int(e^*cl(P)))} = e^*int(e^*cl(P)) = P$. But this is a contradiction to (v). Therefore (X, T) is IFe^* -super connected space.

(v) \Rightarrow (vi): Let P and Q be IFe^* -closed sets in (X, T) such that $P \neq \mathbb{1} \neq Q, Q = \overline{e^*int(P)}$ and $P = \overline{e^*int(Q)}$. Taking $C = \overline{P}$ and $D = \overline{Q}$, C and D become IFe^* -open sets in (X, T) and $C \neq \mathbb{0} \neq D, \overline{e^*cl(C)} = \overline{e^*cl(\overline{P})} = \overline{(e^*int(\overline{P}))} = e^*int(P) = \overline{Q} = D$ and similarly $\overline{e^*cl(D)} = C$. But this is a contradiction to (v). Hence (vi) is true.

(vi) \Rightarrow (i): We can prove this by the similar way as in (v) \Rightarrow (vi). □

Proposition 3.7. Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be a IFe^* -irresolute surjection. If X is an IFe^* -super connected, then so is Y .

Proof. Suppose that Y is IFe*-super disconnected. Then there exists IFe*OS's C and D in Y such that $C \neq \emptyset \neq D$, $C \subseteq \overline{D}$. Since f is IFe*-irresolute, $f^{-1}(C)$ and $f^{-1}(D)$ are IFe*OS's in X and $C \subseteq \overline{D}$ implies $f^{-1}(C) \subseteq f^{-1}(D) = \overline{f^{-1}(D)}$. Hence $f^{-1}(C) \neq \emptyset \neq f^{-1}(\overline{D})$ which means that X is IFe*-super disconnected which is a contradiction. \square

Definition 3.22. An IFTS (X, T) is called intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connected between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q if there is no IFe*OS E in (X, T) such that $P \subseteq E$ and $E\overline{q}Q$.

Example 3.23. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.6}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.6}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.2}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, P is IFe*OS in (X, T) . Then (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected between P and Q .

Theorem 3.8. If an IFTS (X, T) is an intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connected between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q , then it is intuitionistic fuzzy C_5 -connected between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q .

Proof. Suppose (X, T) is not intuitionistic fuzzy C_5 -connected between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets P and Q then there exists an IFOS E in (X, T) such that $P \subseteq E$ and $E\overline{q}Q$. Since every IFOS in IFe*OS, there exists an IFe*OS E in (X, T) such that $P \subseteq E$ and $E\overline{q}Q$ which implies (X, T) is not intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected between P and Q , a contradiction to our hypothesis. Therefore, (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy C_5 -connected between P and Q . \square

However, the converse of the above Theorem is need not be true, as shown by the following example.

Example 3.24. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.2}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.6}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.4}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.4}) \rangle, x \in X \}$ P is IFOS in (X, T) . Then (X, T) intuitionistic fuzzy C_5 -connected between Q and R . Consider IFS $D = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, D is an IFe*OS such that $Q \subseteq D$ and $D \subseteq \overline{R}$ which implies (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -disconnected between Q and R .

Theorem 3.9. Let (X, T) be an IFTS and P and Q be intuitionistic fuzzy sets in (X, T) . If PqQ then (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connected between P and Q .

Proof. Suppose (X, T) is not intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connected between P and Q . Then there exists an IFe*OS E in (X, T) such that $P \subseteq E$ and $E \subseteq \overline{Q}$. This implies that $P \subseteq \overline{Q}$. That is $P\overline{q}Q$ which is a contradiction to our hypothesis. Therefore (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connected between P and Q . \square

However, the converse of the above Theorem is need not be true, as shown by the following example.

Example 3.25. In Example 3.5, Consider the intuitionistic fuzzy sets $Q = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.6}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, $R = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.6}) \rangle, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.2}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, P is IFeOS in (X, T) . Then (X, T) is intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected between P and Q . But P is not q -coincident with Q , since $\mu_P(x) < \nu_Q(x)$.

Definition 3.26. Let N be an IFS in IFTS (X, T)

(a) If there exists intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets M and W in X satisfying the following properties, then N is called IFe* C_i -disconnected (i=1,2,3,4):

$$e^*C_1 : N \subseteq M \cup W, M \cap W \subseteq \overline{N}, N \cap M \neq \emptyset, N \cap W \neq \emptyset,$$

$$e^*C_2 : N \subseteq M \cup W, N \cap M \cap W = \emptyset, N \cap M \neq \emptyset, N \cap W \neq \emptyset,$$

$e^*C_3 : N \subseteq M \cup W, M \cap W \subseteq \overline{N}, M \not\subseteq \overline{N}, W \not\subseteq \overline{N},$
 $e^*C_4 : N \subseteq M \cup W, N \cap M \cap W = \emptyset, M \not\subseteq \overline{N}, W \not\subseteq \overline{N},$
 (b) N is said to be IFe^*C_i -connected ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) if N is not IFe^*C_i -disconnected ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$).

Obviously, we can obtain the following implications between several types of IFe^*C_i -connected ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$):

Example 3.27. In Example 3.5, $M = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}) \rangle, x \in X \}, W = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, be IFe^*OS . Consider the IFS $N = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, N is IFe^*C_2 -connected, IFe^*C_3 -connected, IFe^*C_4 -connected but IFe^*C_1 -disconnected.

Example 3.28. In Example 3.5, $M = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{1}) \rangle, x \in X \}, W = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0}, \frac{b}{1}), (\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, be IFe^*OS . Consider the IFS $N = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, N is IFe^*C_2 -disconnected but IFe^*C_4 -connected.

Example 3.29. In Example 3.5, $M = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.7}), (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.1}) \rangle, x \in X \}, W = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.8}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, be IFe^*OS . Consider the IFS $N = \{ \langle x, (\frac{a}{0.2}, \frac{b}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}) \rangle, x \in X \}$, N is IFe^*C_3 -disconnected but IFe^*C_4 -connected.

4. INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY e^* -EXTREMALLY DISCONNECTEDNESS IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 4.1. Let (X, T) be any IFTS. X is called IFe^* -extremally disconnected if the e^* -closure of every IFe^*OS in X is IFe^*OS .

Theorem 4.1. For an IFTS (X, T) the following are equivalent:

- (i) (X, T) is an IFe^* -extremally disconnected space.
- (ii) For each $\text{IFe}^*\text{CS } P$, $e^*\text{int}(P)$ is an IFe^*CS .
- (iii) For each $\text{IFe}^*\text{OS } P$, $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)}$ is an IFe^*CS .
- (iv) For each intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets P and Q with $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{Q}$, $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)}$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Let P be any IFe^*CS . Then \overline{P} is an IFe^*OS . So $e^*\text{cl}(\overline{P}) = \overline{e^*\text{int}(P)}$ is an IFe^*OS . Thus $e^*\text{int}(P)$ is an IFe^*CS in (X, T) .

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let P be an IFe^*OS . Then $e^*\text{cl}(\overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)}) = e^*\text{cl}(e^*\text{int}(\overline{P}))$, $\overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)} = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(e^*\text{int}(\overline{P}))}$. Since P is an IFe^*OS , \overline{P} is an IFe^*CS . So by (ii) $e^*\text{int}(\overline{P})$ is an IFe^*CS . That is $e^*\text{cl}(e^*\text{int}(\overline{P})) = e^*\text{int}(\overline{P})$. Hence $e^*\text{cl}(e^*\text{int}(\overline{P})) = e^*\text{int}(\overline{P}) = e^*\text{cl}(P)$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv): Let P and Q be any two intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open sets in (X, T) such that $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{Q}$. (iii) implies $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)} = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(Q)} = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(Q)}$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i): Let P be any IFe^*OS in (X, T) . Put $Q = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(P)}$. Then $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{Q}$. Hence by (iv) $e^*\text{cl}(P) = \overline{e^*\text{cl}(Q)}$. Therefore $e^*\text{cl}(P)$ is IFe^*OS in (X, T) . That is (X, T) is an IFe^* -extremally disconnected space. \square

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced and studied the concept of types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -connected and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -extremally disconnected in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces are introduced and studied. Here we introduce the concepts of intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_5 -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_S -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_M -connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -strongly connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -super connectedness, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*C_i -connectedness ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$), and obtained several properties and some characterizations concerning connectedness in these spaces.

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